

REPORT: Characterisation of the discharge coefficient of CFVNs for different gases

A2.1.5

Authors: G. Bobovnik, P. Sambol, J. Kutin

Confidentiality: Public

Submission date: 16.2.2022

Revision: 1.0

methyinfra.ptb.de

Report Characterisation of the discharge coefficient of CFVNs for different gases	
Funding European Metrology Program for Innovation and Research	Grant agreement no: 20IND11
Project name Metrology infrastructure for high-pressure gas and liquified hydrogen flows	Project short name MetHyInfra
Author(s) Gregor Bobovnik, University of Ljubljana, Faculty of Mechanical Engineering, Ljubljana, Email: gregor.bobovnik@fs.uni-lj.si Peter Sambol, University of Ljubljana, Faculty of Mechanical Engineering, Ljubljana, Email: peter.sambol@fs.uni-lj.si Jože Kutin, University of Ljubljana, Faculty of Mechanical Engineering, Ljubljana, Email: joze.kutin@fs.uni-lj.si	Pages 15 pages
Summary This report was written as part of activity 2.1.5 from the EMPIR Metrology infrastructure for high-pressure gas and liquified hydrogen flows (MetHyInfra) project. The three-year European project commenced on 1 st June 2021 and focused on providing solutions to four measurement challenges faced by the hydrogen industry (high pressure flow meter calibration for mobility (1000 bar / 3.6 kg/min), fuel cells applications (4 kg/h, 30 bar) and liquid hydrogen. We are looking for letters of support from the hydrogen industry). For more details about this project please visit methyinfra.ptb.de .	
Confidentiality	Public

This project “Metrology infrastructure for high-pressure gas and liquified hydrogen flows” (MetHyInfra) has received funding from the EMPIR programme co-financed by the Participating States and from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant agreement No [20IND11].

EMPIR

The EMPIR initiative is co-funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme and the EMPIR Participating States

1 Contents

2	Introduction.....	3
3	Measurement system and measurement procedure	3
4	Calculation of the discharge coefficient.....	7
5	Results	8
5.1	Discharge coefficient model according to ISO 9300	8
5.2	Interpretation of experimental data	10
6	Discussion.....	13
7	References.....	14

2 Introduction

The study deals with calibration and characterisation of the discharge coefficient of three toroidal critical flow venturi nozzles (CFVNs) of different dimensions with six different gases (dry air, argon, helium, hydrogen, nitrogen, nitrous oxide). Based on comparison and analysis of experimental results, the study will try to identify potential alternative to hydrogen gas in the calibration process. The results will also be used for selection of alternative gas in the inter-comparison of alternative fluids in activity A2.4.2.

The discharge coefficient C_d of the nozzle is in general defined as

$$C_d = \frac{q_m}{q_{m,id}}, \quad (1)$$

where q_m is the actual mass flow rate and $q_{m,id}$ so-called ideal critical mass flow rate (assuming the one-dimensional isentropic flow of ideal gas). The ideal mass flow rate is defined by

$$q_{m,id} = \frac{AC^* p_0}{\sqrt{R_m T_0}}, \quad (2)$$

where A is cross-section at the nozzle throat, C^* is the critical flow function, R_m is the specific gas constant, p_0 and T_0 are the stagnation pressure and temperature, respectively.

The value of the discharge coefficient is related to the viscous effects of the boundary layer (C_{d1}) and the core flow defined by the geometry of the nozzle (C_{d2}) [1,2]. Because the coefficients are almost independent of each other, the discharge coefficient can be approximated as:

$$C_d \approx C_{d1} C_{d2} = a - \frac{b}{Re^n}, \quad (3)$$

where the coefficients a , b and n are related to the geometry of the nozzle and the type of the gas and Re is throat Reynolds number based on ideal mass flow rate of the gas:

$$Re = \frac{4q_{m,id}}{\pi d \eta_0}, \quad (4)$$

where d is nozzle throat diameter and η_0 is the dynamic viscosity of the gas at stagnation inlet conditions.

The expression (3) for the discharge coefficient has the form that is also used in ISO 9300 [3] for standardized nozzle shapes (for toroidal nozzles according the value of $n = 0.5$, while for cylindrical nozzles $n = 0.2$).

3 Measurement system and measurement procedure

The tests were carried out for three toroidal critical flow venturi nozzles with three different throat diameters (d), which are part of 5-nozzle array (Tetratec) with the inlet manifold diameter of $D = 10$ mm:

- nozzle 1; $d_1 = 0.175$ mm;
- nozzle 2; $d_2 = 0.275$ mm;
- nozzle 3; $d_3 = 0.436$ mm.

where the given diameters d are the values measured by the manufacturer of the nozzles. The tests were carried out in October and November of 2021 in Laboratory of Measurements in Process Engineering at Faculty of Mechanical Engineering in Ljubljana. The setup used for tests is shown schematically in Figure 1. High pressure cylinders (50 L) were used as a gas source. The pressure regulator (stage 1) was mounted at the outlet of the gas cylinder and was set to approximately 1 MPa. In order to achieve suitable temperature stabilization, the gas passed through a tube coil before reaching the pressure controller (Bronkhorst, EL-PRESS P-502C), which was used to set the inlet absolute pressure of CFVNs in the interval between 200 kPa and 700 kPa. The pressure (Mensor, CGP2500 & CPR2550, $U(k=2) = 0.02\%$ MV or 80 Pa) and the temperature (Tetratec & PicoTechnology; 535T 161 & PT-104, $U(k=2) = 0.2\%$ °C) of the gas were measured at the inlet manifold of the CFVNs. The piston prover (Sierra Instruments (Bios), Cal=Trak SL-800 & SL-800-44, $U(k=2) = 0.14\%$), which was used as a standard, was connected to the outlet of the CFVNs.

Figure 1: Scheme of the test setup

All components were connected to the PC with control program realized in LabVIEW environment. Using the program, it was possible to control the pressure at the CFVNs inlet and save all necessary data for further processing. The reference mass flow rate was determined as the average of ten consecutive readings of the piston prover.

The measurements for each CFVN were carried out at six measurement points; at nominal inlet pressures p_1 equal to (200, 300, 400, 500, 600, 700) kPa. Three repetitions were carried out at each measuring point. The reference mass flow rate is determined as the mean of ten consecutive readings of the piston prover. The results at each measurement point consist of three main parameters:

- $q_{m,ref}$ – reference mass flow rate,
- p_1 – pressure at the inlet of the CFVN,
- T_1 – temperature at the inlet of the CFVN.

The calibration of the nozzles was carried out with six different gases (the grade of purity of each gas is shown in parentheses):

- dry air,
- Ar - argon (5.0),

Characterisation of the discharge coefficient of CFVNs for different gases

- He - helium (5.6),
- H₂ - hydrogen (5.5),
- N₂ - nitrogen (5.0),
- N₂O - nitrous oxide (2.5).

Special precautions were made for working with hydrogen. First, prior to using the hydrogen the leak-tightness of all connections were tested with helium using a He-sniffer device. During the measurements of hydrogen, the part of the measuring system (CFVNs, the pressure controller and the piston prover) were put under the fume hood as shown in Figure 2. Using the suitable ventilation system, the gas under the fume hood was exhausted into the outdoor environment.

Figure 2: Measuring system with fume hood

All properties of gases were defined using REFPROP v9.0 database [4]. The main physical properties of gases (density, dynamic viscosity, critical flow function and isentropic exponent κ) are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Properties of the gases at 293.15 K and 300 kPa

Gas	ρ	η	C^*	κ
	kg/m ³	Pas	/	/
air	3,569	18,235	0,6857	1,406
Ar	4,927	22,341	0,7276	1,676
H ₂	0,248	8,818	0,6865	1,406
He	0,492	19,625	0,7259	1,666
N ₂	3,450	17,600	0,6855	1,405
N ₂ O	5,512	14,658	0,6699	1,295

The expected ranges of Re number for given nozzle and different gases in the inlet pressure range between 200 kPa and 700 kPa are shown in Figures 3 – 5.

Characterisation of the discharge coefficient of CFVNs for different gases

Figure 3. Nozzle 1 – Re range for different gases in the considered range of inlet pressure

Figure 4. Nozzle 2 – Re range for different gases in the considered range of inlet pressure

Figure 5. Nozzle 3 – Re range for different gases in the considered range of inlet pressure

4 Calculation of the discharge coefficient

The discharge coefficient at each measurement point is calculated according to eq. (1) using $q_{m,ref}$ as the actual flow rate determined by the piston prover. To determine the ideal mass flow rate (2), first the stagnation temperature (T_0) and pressure (p_0) are calculated as:

$$p_0 = p_1 \left(1 + \frac{\kappa - 1}{2} Ma_1^2 \right)^{\frac{\kappa}{\kappa - 1}}, \quad (5)$$

$$T_0 = T_1 \left(1 + \frac{\kappa - 1}{2} Ma_1^2 \right),$$

where κ is isentropic exponent and Ma_1 is Mach number at the inlet conditions (at upstream pressure tapping). The cross-section at the throat of CFVN is calculated as $A = \pi d^2/4$.

The coefficients a , b and n are determined by fitting the calculated discharge coefficients vs Re according to ISO model (3). The value of n was in all cases rounded to two decimal places.

The uncertainty of calculated discharge coefficient is given by:

$$\frac{U(C_d)}{C_d} \approx 2 \sqrt{\left(\frac{u(q_{m,ref})}{q_{m,ref}} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{u(p_1)}{p_1} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{1}{2} \frac{u(T_1)}{T_1} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{u(C_d)}{C_d} \right)_{approx.}^2}, \quad (6)$$

where the last term represents the uncertainty of the approximation.

5 Results

5.1 Discharge coefficient model according to ISO 9300

The experimentally obtained values of discharge coefficients for all three nozzles and all the gases under consideration together with their approximations (3) are shown in Figures 6 to 8. The values of coefficients a , b and n of the C_d models for all three nozzles are listed in Table 2. The uncertainties of the resulting discharge coefficients were approximately 0,2 % in all cases.

It can be seen that similar trends (differences between gases) of discharge coefficients for different gases are observed for nozzles 1 and 3, whereas this is not the case for nozzle 2. In the case of nozzle 2 with nitrous oxide, the values of the discharge coefficient tend to decrease with Re and are even greater than one. Also the values of coefficients b and n given in Table 2 show that nozzle 2 behaves differently than other two nozzles and probably cannot be characterized as a standard toroidal nozzle. Besides relatively poor repeatability, also a significant hysteresis was observed during the tests in case of nozzle 2, therefore the further comparisons and analyses will only be made for the experimental results obtained for nozzles 1 and 3.

As evident in Section 2 there is a relatively small range of Re where the determined discharge coefficients could be directly compared. However, the values of discharge coefficients of air, nitrogen and hydrogen almost overlap for nozzles 1 and 3. The results also show that compared to nitrogen (or air or hydrogen) the discharge coefficient for argon and helium is about 0.5 % lower, while it is about 1 % higher for nitrous oxide. A bit smaller values of C_d for helium and argon agree with some earlier experimental data published in [5,6].

Figure 6. C_d for different gases for nozzle 1 – experiments (symbols) & C_d model (lines)

Figure 7. C_d for different gases for nozzle 2 - experiments (symbols) & C_d model (lines)

Figure 8. C_d for different gases for nozzle 3 – experiments (symbols) & C_d model (lines)

Table 2. Values of coefficients a , b and n for all three nozzles and different gases

Gas	a	b	n
Nozzle 1			
air	1,00118	4,0332	0,47
Ar	1,00040	3,9571	0,46
H ₂	0,99907	3,8839	0,47
He	0,98907	6,2386	0,53
N ₂	1,00231	3,7804	0,46
N ₂ O	0,99779	2,2615	0,44
Nozzle 2			
air	0,98559	2,0651E+07	2,41
Ar	0,98252	7,2428E+05	2,01
H ₂	0,97821	6,4047E+05	2,14
He	0,99634	3,3602E+00	0,52
N ₂	0,98519	7,9580E+07	2,56
N ₂ O	0,99604	-7,2051E-02	0,31
Nozzle 3			
air	0,99170	26,987	0,74
Ar	0,98833	49,051	0,80
H ₂	0,99556	6,5126	0,58
He	1,00020	5,3843	0,53
N ₂	0,98956	62,938	0,84
N ₂ O	0,99696	16,254	0,74

5.2 Interpretation of experimental data

First, we made the comparison with C_d for accurately machined toroidal nozzles ($a = 0.9985$, $b = 3.412$ and $n = 0,5$) according to ISO 9300 [3]. The comparison for nozzles 1 and 3 is shown in Figures 9 and 10, respectively. For nozzle 3 the ISO 9300 model almost exactly matches the values of air, nitrogen and hydrogen, whereas for nozzle 1 the ISO 9300 model predicts higher values of C_d than those obtained in tests. Note, that ISO 9300 states validity of C_d model only for $Re > 21,000$. Besides, the observed difference for nozzle 1 could also result from some error in the value of the throat diameter. Our analysis shows that the actual diameter of nozzle 1 is probably about 0.001 mm smaller than its specified value.

Figure 9. Comparison of experimental values for C_d and ISO 9300 model for nozzle 1

Figure 10. Comparison of experimental values for C_d and ISO 9300 model for nozzle 3

The ISO 9300 model agrees well with the experimental trends of the discharge coefficient, but does not explain the differences between different gases. Based on the measured values of the discharge coefficients, the gases can be classified into three groups (from lowest to highest values of C_d): (i) helium and argon, (ii) air, nitrogen and hydrogen and (iii) nitrous oxide. As given in Table 1 the gases

Characterisation of the discharge coefficient of CFVNs for different gases

belonging to one of these three groups can be characterized by a similar value of isentropic exponent; for helium and argon it is about 1.67, for air, nitrogen and hydrogen about 1.4 and for nitrous oxide its value is about 1.3.

This can be partly explained by comparison of experimental values with the C_d model according to Ishibashi and Takamoto [1], which takes into account the isentropic coefficient:

$$a = 1 - \frac{\kappa + 1}{(2R/d)^2} \left(\frac{1}{96} - \frac{8\kappa + 21}{4608(2R/d)} + \frac{754 + 1971\kappa + 2007}{552960(2R/d)^2} \right) \text{ and} \quad (7)$$

$$b = \frac{4a}{\sqrt{m}} \left(\frac{\kappa + 1}{2} \right)^{\frac{1}{2} \frac{1}{\kappa + 1}} \left(3\sqrt{2} - 2\sqrt{3} + \frac{\kappa - 1}{\sqrt{3}} \right),$$

where

$$m = \sqrt{\frac{2d}{R} \left(\frac{\kappa + 1}{2} \right)^{\frac{3\kappa - 1}{\kappa - 1}}}, \quad (8)$$

and $R = 2d$ is the wall curvature of the nozzle throat. The comparison for hydrogen, helium and nitrous oxide is shown in Figure 11 for nozzle 3. It is evident that the difference between measured C_d values for gases from group (i) and group (ii) can be well explained by Ishibashi&Takamoto model. These is accordance with [5] where the experimental data for hydrogen, nitrogen and argon agreed reasonably well with the Ishibashi&Takamoto model. Also Tang and Fenn [7] found that C_d for nitrogen, hydrogen, argon and helium coincide with their proposed model at $Re > 1000$, which also exhibits dependence of C_d on κ .

On the other hand, the values of C_d for nitrous oxide cannot be explained by the Ishibashi&Takamoto model, which predicts increase of C_d of only about 0.1 % compared to hydrogen. Much larger observed difference in the experimental results could result from relatively low purity (99.5%) of nitrous oxide or the effects of vibrational relaxation; see e.g. [6,8,9] for vibrational relaxation effects in CO_2 and SF_6 .

Figure 11. Comparison of C_d for different gases for nozzle 3
(—●— experimental data; --- Ishibashi&Takamoto model [1])

6 Discussion

The discharge coefficients (C_d) were experimentally determined for six different gases (air, argon, helium, hydrogen, nitrogen and nitrous oxide) and three different toroidal CFVNs with throat diameters from 0.175 mm to 0.436 mm. The measurements for each CFVN were carried out at absolute inlet pressures in the interval from 200 kPa to 700 kPa, which covers the range of Re numbers from about 2000 to 60,000. The results obtained are as follows:

- nozzle 2 showed poor repeatability and large deviation from the expected values of coefficients b and n from ISO 9300 based C_d model. The nozzle was therefore excluded from further analysis;
- values of C_d were found to be dependent on isentropic coefficient of the gas, which agrees with the predictions of theoretical models, e.g. [1];
- values of C_d for hydrogen, air and nitrogen agree well with the standard ISO 9300 model. However, it might not be possible to achieve comparable ranges of Re number for hydrogen and air or nitrogen for given CFVN;
- for helium and argon, the values of C_d were found to be about 0.5 % smaller than for air, nitrogen or hydrogen. Though, this difference can be compensated using the model, which takes into account the isentropic coefficient. Besides, the Re number range of helium is very comparable to that of hydrogen;
- the highest values of C_d were observed for nitrous oxide (about 1 % higher than for air) and this deviation cannot be explained solely by the influence of the isentropic coefficient.

7 References

- [1] M. Ishibashi, M. Takamoto, Theoretical discharge coefficient of a critical circular-arc nozzle with laminar boundary layer and its verification by measurements using super-accurate nozzles, *Flow Measurement and Instrumentation*, Vol. 11 (4), 2000.
- [2] B. Mickan, Discharge coefficients of CFVN predicted for high Reynolds numbers based on low-Re-calibration, *Flow Measurement and Instrumentation*, Vol. 78, 2021.
- [3] ISO 9300-2005: Measurement of gas flow by means of critical flow Venturi nozzles.
- [4] E.W. Lemmon, M.L. Huber and M.O. McLinden, 2010 NIST Reference Fluid Thermodynamic and Transport Properties—REFPROP Version 9.0 (Gaithersburg, MD: National Institute of Standards and Technology).
- [5] A.N. Johnson et al., Numerical characterization of the discharge coefficient in critical nozzles, 1998 NCSL Workshop & Symposium.
- [6] A.N. Johnson et al., Relaxation Effects in Small Critical Nozzles, *Journal of Fluids Engineering*, Vol. 128(1), 2006.
- [7] S.P. Tang, J.B. Fenn, Experimental Determination of the Discharge Coefficients for Critical Flow through an Axisymmetric Nozzle, *AIAA Journal*, Vol. 16 (1), 1978.
- [8] Johnson A.N. et al., The effect of vibrational relaxation on the discharge coefficient of critical flow venturis, *Flow Measurement and Instrumentation*, Vol 11, 2000.
- [9] J. Nagao et al., Numerical study on characteristics of real gas flow through a critical nozzle, *International Journal of Turbo & Jet-Engines*, Vol. 29 (1), 2012.